

Optimization of Multiple Sequence Alignment Software ClustalW

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Abstract

This activity with the project PRACE-2IP is aimed to investigate and improve the performance of multiple sequence alignment software ClustalW on the supercomputer BlueGene/Q, so-called JUQUEEN, for the case study of the influenza virus sequences. Porting, tuning, profiling, and scaling of this code has been accomplished in this aspect. A parallel I/O interface has been designed for efficient sequence dataset input, in which sub-groups' local masters take care of read operation and broadcast the dataset to their slaves. The optimal group size has been investigated and the effects of read buffer size on read performance has been experimented. The application to ClustalW software shows that the current implementation with parallel I/O provides considerably better performance than the original code in view of I/O segment, leading up to 6.8 times speed-up for inputting dataset in case of using 8192 JUQUEEN cores.

1. Overview of the Project

The study of the variability of influenza virus is of great importance nowadays. The world DNA databases are accessible for common use and usually contain information for more than one (up to several thousands) individual genomes for each species. Until now 84049 isolates of influenza virus have been sequenced and are available through GenBank [1].

In silico biological sequence processing is a key technology for molecular biology. Scientists are now dependent on databases and access to the biological information. This scientific area requires powerful computing resources for exploring large sets of biological data.

The parallel implementation of methods and algorithms for analysis of biological data using high-performance computing is essential to accelerate the research and reduce the financial cost. Multiple sequence alignment (MSA) is an important method for biological sequences analysis and involves more than two biological sequences, generally of the protein, DNA, or RNA type. This method is computationally difficult and is classified as a NP-hard problem. ClustalW software has become the most popular algorithm and implements a progressive method for multiple sequence alignment [2]. ClustalW computes the best match for the selected sequences, and lines them up so that the identities, similarities and differences can be seen. The basic algorithm behind ClustalW proceeds in three stages: pairwise alignment (PA), guide tree (GT) and multiple alignment (MA). Pairwise alignment computes the optimal alignment cost for each pairs of sequences. A distance matrix is built up the entries of which show the degree of divergence for each pair of sequences in evolution. Distance is calculated as the percentage of nonidentity residues between two sequences. An evolutionary tree is out of the distance matrix using the sequence similarity matrix and Neighbor-Joining algorithm [3]. The tree holds values for each sequence that represent its similarity to all other sequences. The algorithm aligns the sequences progressively according to the branching order in the guide tree by first aligning the most similar pair of sequences, then the next most similar pair and so on. ClustalW phases are relatively independent. Each of the phases produces intermediate data which is used as an input for the next one. The execution time is strongly dependent on the number of sequences as well as their size. ClustalW-MPI [4] is a distributed and parallel implementation on a distributed computer clusters and on the traditional parallel computers.

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The computational aspect of this project is to investigate the parallel performance in respect to the efficiency, scaling and profiling of parallel multiple alignment on the supercomputer JUQUEEN [5] utilizing parallel I/O deployment and optimization of MPI-based parallel implementation of ClustalW algorithm for the case study of influenza viral sequences comparison.

2. Parallel I/O Deployment to the ClustalW-MPI Software

a. MPI-I/O

Parallel I/O strategy is getting a lot of attention these days, due to more requirement of handling massive data input and outputs during a single simulation run. The main idea is to enable multiple processes to concurrently access the single file for I/O operation, so that the additional overhead of distributing/gathering the global dataset in traditional I/O approach can be diminished. A couple of parallel I/O implementations are in use these days, as depicted in Figure 2. MPI-I/O [6] has been standardized in 1997 and open source implementation of ROMIO [7] is commonly used by most MPI libraries. Parallel NetCDF [8] and parallel HDF5 [9] are implemented on top of MPI-I/O for the purpose of providing easier controllability and higher portability. On the other hand, these two implementations only allow the parallel I/O operations of the specific file format. Therefore, we directly impose the raw MPI-I/O functions to the current application for parallel I/O operation of genetic sequence dataset.

Figure 1 The Parallel I/O Software Stack (Referenced by W. Frings, M. Stephan, F. Janetzko in [11])

The parallel MPI I/O model for simultaneous and independent access to single file collectively is presented in Figure 2. The slaves read the input sequences and output results to the file collectively. Even if the file system lacks support for parallel operations, this process is still more efficient, as slaves conduct more work in parallel (i.e. slaves complete their own results rather than relying on the master to do it).

Figure 2 Parallel MPI I/O Programming Model for Simultaneous and Independent Access to Single File Collectively

Since the crude MPI-I/O function is directly applied to the application code, performance can vary a lot depending on the maturity of implementation. First, some tunable parameters do exist in the middleware layer, which are handled by `MPI_Info_set`. Out of them, `cb_buffer_size` and `cb_nodes` are two noticeable parameters which affect the actual read/write speed. `cb_buffer_size` controls the size (in bytes) of the intermediate buffer, whose default is 4194304 (4 Mbytes). `cb_nodes` represents the maximum number of aggregators, which is set to the number of unique hosts in the communicator used when opening the file by default. We tune those parameters after multiple benchmark runs.

Another remarkable parameters which strongly affect parallel I/O performance are the number of processors participating in I/O calls and the size of read request from a single I/O call. Depending on the size of the dataset, the parallel I/O operation by all ranks might result in poorer performance compared with the composition of a serial read and collective communication. Therefore, we restrict the number of I/O ranks out of total processors. This is implemented by dividing the whole processors into several groups through the creation of MPI sub-communicators. We let master ranks of individual group to perform the I/O operation and to do collective operation with their slave processors. The optimal size of the group can differ depending on the total number of processors, I/O sizes, and computer hardware. Likewise, the size of read request per a single I/O call (which we will call as ‘read buffer size’) affects the read performance. In general, a larger read chunk size gives back the better performance because it necessitates less `MPI_read` function call. However, the read buffer size is limited by the file server’s specification, since the same-sized array shall be created in the file server for passing the data. As more ranks participate in parallel I/O calls, individual read buffer size should be reduced to maintain the total memory consumption in a file server. Therefore, the design of a read buffer size becomes related with the determination of the group size. The synthetic benchmark code for acquiring the best condition of group size and read buffer size is attached in ‘Appendix A: Implementation of grouped I/O operation through the creation of sub-communicators’.

b. Deployment of the Parallel I/O to ClustalW-MPI Software

ClustalW-MPI [4] is a MPI-parallelized version of ClustalW software. Clustal family of codes [2] are tools for aligning multiple nucleic acid and protein sequences. The alignment is achieved via three steps: pairwise alignment, guide-tree generation and progressive alignment. [4]

ClustalW-MPI adopts the master-slave parallelism (Figure 3) in which master stores all global dataset, interfaces to I/O operations, and schedules slaves’ tasks. The benefit of this parallelism is that the load balancing is easily achieved for embarrassingly parallel tasks (pairwise alignment in this code), because master dynamically assigns the task to slaves in the runtime. On the other hand, the master rank easily exposes the memory overflow since all resultants are stored in the master, and the cost for master-slave communication becomes a bottleneck. In view of I/O in this code, master processor takes care of all POSIX-styled, sequential I/O operations and performs the point-to-point communication with individual slave to send/receive those I/O datasets. This implementation makes it impossible to directly impose MPI-I/O formulation in this code, since MPI-I/O functions are collective

operations among the whole processors in the same communicator. Therefore, to enable parallel I/O, the code should be reconstructed so that the I/O-related routines are visible by all processors.

The objective of parallel read implementation is to replace the initial send/rcv operation of passing the global sequence dataset with the advanced and direct data access among all processors. To capacitate it, we make the file-read routine (*readseq* function) and other related input functions to be accessed by slaves. Also, the initial send/rcv operation is redesigned to exclude the sequence-related datasets. As to be demonstrated in Chapter 3.a, the parallel read via groups results in a notably better performance compared with the composition of sequential read and broadcast operations. However, in ClustalW-MPI code, the performance improvement by this parallel read is not recognizable since the cost of getting input dataset is quite negligible compared to the total simulation time. We rather value the current implementation for providing the stable and fast way of storing multiple sequence inputs, capacitating the alignment simulation of massive sequence datasets. Nevertheless, as to be presented in Chapter 3.b, the current implementation could be experimented up to O(10) MB dataset in ClustalW-MPI software, due to its massive memory requirement from the master processor. The master processor allocates a 2-D, double-precision matrix, called *mat*, whose size is $\text{sizeof}(\text{double}) \times \text{number_of_sequences} \times \text{number_of_sequences}$. It easily exceeds the memory limit of BlueGene/Q system (1 GB per rank) if the total number of analyzed sequences is more than 10,000. It emphasizes the strong necessity of changing the current master-slave parallelism to a domain decomposition method.

Figure 3 The Master-Slave Parallelism in ClustalW-MPI

The master-slave parallelism of this code precludes the further implementation of parallel writing functionality. The progressive alignment result from each slave is stored to the alignment output file after additional analysis from the master processor. Incorporating parallel write induces the additional overhead of broadcasting other referenced variables after the progressive alignment stage. Considering the size of currently analyzable datasets, the parallel write operation would show poorer performance compared to the current serial way of file writing. Therefore, parallel write implementation shall be explored after the main parallelism has changed.

3. Performance Results

a. Benchmark Performance of Parallel I/O for Sequence Alignment

Parallel read by all CPU ranks often leads to the excessive overhead on the file system so that ROMIO results in memory overflow. Therefore, determining on ‘how many ranks concurrently operate file I/O’ (i.e., size of the group) and ‘how large a single operation shall read the chunk of the data’ (i.e., size of read buffer) shall be preceded. Also, the determination of tuning parameters shall accompany.

We experiment on JUQUEEN [5] supercomputer which equips the GPFS (General Parallel File System). Each compute node contains 16 cores which supports 4-way hyperthreading (use up to 64 ranks-per-node) and 16 GB RAM is installed. Experiments have been performed at 128 BlueGene/Q nodes, varying ranks-per-nodes to 8, 16 and 32. Read dataset (Human_4_8999.fa) is roughly 16 Mbyte, which is the biggest possible data size to be run on ClustalW-MPI code (in condition of assigning 1 GB RAM per rank).

1) Effect of the Group Size

We measure the parallel read performance by varying the size of the group from 1 to 1024. Under each group, only master of that group participates in collective read operation and broadcasts the dataset to its local slaves. Thus, large group size implies that small number of processors participate in actual read operation. Size of read buffer is set to 16M, so that the whole dataset is read after a single read operation.

Table 1 presents the parallel read performance at various sizes of groups. The result describes the total time consumption (in second) for completing the data input process, which is the sum of 100 repetitions. The first notable feature is that MPI-I/O itself provides better performance compared to the POSIX-type sequential read and broadcast operation. In case of using 8 ranks-per-node, total number of ranks is the same as the group size, so that the parallel I/O internally operates the identical procedure as the sequential read + broadcast operation. However, from the performance comparison, the same operation via MPI-I/O returns 4 times faster result than that of POSIX-based operation. The second feature is that, generally, large group size benefits more by the parallel read. The result globally expresses that the best performance is achieved when number of I/O processors are 4 ~ 8. It implies that parallel I/O participants shall be maintained around the half of *cb_nodes* value (in this experiment, *cb_nodes* was set as 18 by default.). Lastly, the parallel I/O operation can easily overflow the memory bound in ROMIO. As the group size lessens, the I/O cost increases and finally ROMIO results in the memory overflow. That memory overflow becomes much more significant as the number of total ranks increases. From this experiment, we argue that the number of I/O processors shall be maintained in O(1) level on Juqueen.

		Group Size						
		Serial Read	1	4	16	64	256	1024
Ranks per Node (Ranks in Total)	8 (1024)	60.08424	OoM	104.354	32.52894	15.74773	10.46931	15.82539
	16 (2048)	61.08526	OoM	OoM	56.19771	22.37062	12.86353	19.8647
	32 (4096)	66.88894	OoM	OoM	OoM	37.79991	20.33754	14.71392

Table 1 Parallel Read Wall-time at 128 Juqueen Nodes with the Dataset of 16MByte. OoM denotes ‘out of memory’ from ROMIO. Result describes the cost of file read + broadcast, which is the sum of 100 repetitions. The unit of the result is second.

2) Effect of the Read Buffer Size

The same experiment has been performed to figure out the effect of read buffer size on I/O cost. We fix the size of group to 64 and change the read buffer size from 1 MB to 16 MB. Since the size of dataset is a little less than 16MB, setting the buffer size to 16MB will result in a single MPI_read call. The result at verifies that the best performance is achieved if the whole dataset is read at once. Meanwhile, performances at 1MB read buffer and 4MB read buffer does not differ much, while their number of read operations are 4 times different. It implies that the number of read operation does not affect much on performance as long as the buffer size is smaller than *cb_buffer_size*.

		Read Buffer Size			
		Serial Read	1	4	16
Ranks per Node (Ranks in Total)	8 (1024)	60.2112	39.12143	33.55494	15.76412
	16 (2048)	61.07789	53.38877	51.54913	22.69664
	32 (4096)	66.91325	83.1284	88.99129	38.29796

Table 2 Parallel Read Wall-time at 128 Juqueen Nodes with the Group Size of 64. Result describes the cost of file read + broadcast, which is the sum of 100 repetitions. The unit of the result is second.

Though not presented here, the same test on 139MB dataset exposes other important characteristics of MPI-I/O. First, as we increase the buffer size to 64MB, the read cost significantly reduces (117.88 seconds to 86.98

seconds when ranks-per-node is 8; 166.04 seconds to 102.17 seconds when ranks-per-node is 16). It clarifies that number of MPI_read calls also affect the performance of the read operation. Second, the 64MB read request with ranks-per-node of 32 results in the memory overflow. Remembering that the only difference between 32 ranks-per-node case and other cases is the number of I/O ranks, we shall maintain the global buffer size request (number of I/O ranks * each buffer size) to a certain level. In current condition, that amount shall be less than 4GB, considering that 64MB read size requested by 64 I/O ranks (= 4096 ranks / 64 ranks-per-group) was in failure.

3) Effect of ROMIO's Parameters

Effects of ROMIO parameters on parallel I/O performance are also examined. We fix the group size as 64, read buffer's size as 1 MB and measure the time for reading 16 MB dataset. We experimented on 128 nodes in JUQUEEN, changing its ranks-per-node from 8 to 32. By default, *cb_nodes* is set to 18 and *cb_buffer_size* is set to 16 MB in current configuration. We observe that *cb_nodes* is non-changeable by the system, thus we only experimented by changing *cb_buffer_size* parameter.

We acquire the interesting result, as observed at . We initially expected that a larger buffer size would benefit more, since the number of reading operation can reduce. However, the experiment reveals that the smaller *cb_buffer_size* provides the better performance. It is hard to argue that this is the general characteristics, but we can affirm that the small *cb_buffer_size* is preferred for some applications which inputs the character strings.

		<i>cb_buffer_size</i>			
		Serial Read	1	4	16
Ranks per Node	8 (1024)	60.68055	12.51359	15.49949	15.85908
	16 (2048)	61.61542	17.06368	22.30183	22.6694
(Ranks in Total)	32 (4096)	66.60849	26.88654	37.1918	37.64213

Table 3 Parallel Read Wall-time at 128 Juqueen Nodes with the Group Size of 64 and the Read Buffer Size of 16 MB. Result describes the cost of file read + broadcast, which is the sum of 100 repetitions. The unit of the result is second.

Overall, we get the following conclusion as the best way for acquiring sequence string inputs:

- 1) Comparing the sequential read operation and MPI-I/O read by a single processor, MPI-I/O benefits over the traditional POSIX-type file read.
- 2) Number of I/O ranks shall be maintained less than *cb_nodes* count. Many experiments prove that 4 – 8 I/O ranks benefit most.
- 3) Bigger read buffer size is preferred. It implies that the small number of MPI_read call is better for the performance. Meanwhile, it can encounter the memory overflow from I/O server. The total amount of request (number of I/O ranks × read buffer size) shall be maintained under the I/O server's capacity.
- 4) Reasonably small *cb_buffer_size* is better for bio-informatics codes. We suggest the *cb_buffer_size* to be 1/8th or 1/16th of the system's default value.

b. Parallel Read Performance in the ClustalW-MPI

In the ClustalW-MPI software, the problem size is strictly limited by the number of sequences to be aligned. As has been remarked at Chapter 2.b, the master rank allocates a 2-D, double-precision array which stores the identity percentage between two sequences. Aligning 10,000 sequences is almost the upper bound on JUQUEEN, considering that we use all cores in a single node (without hyperthreading). Since the size of a single sequence string is a few Kilobyte, the global data input to be read is O(10) Megabyte long. Due to this reason, applying the parallel I/O operation does not give back the noticeable change in total simulation time. Nevertheless, the current parallel I/O implementation still values in that it will provide more advanced I/O operations for the highly-parallelized ClustalW codes in the future and this approach is applicable to other sequence alignment implementations.

Understanding this situation, we verify the performance of parallel I/O implementation by comparing the data input time between the original code and the current version. We measure the simulation time until the code is ready to start the actual pairwise alignment analysis. Thus, the measured time includes all initial procedures of parameter setup and memory allocation, as well as data reading and broadcasting. Input data size is 16 Megabyte and it contains 8,999 sequences. We compare the performance at different number of core ranges, from 512 to 8192 cores. According to the result of Chapter 3.a, we design the group size to be 1/8th of total number of cores (so that the number of I/O ranks is maintained to 8) and we set the read buffer size to be 16 Megabyte.

Simulation times by the original ClustalW-MPI code and the current version are presented at Figure 4. To get more accurate result, each experiment was repeated 10 times and the average is depicted. As is verified by the result, the parallel version provides considerably better performance than the original code in all experiments. The performance gain by the parallel read is stronger as the number of cores increases, so that it becomes 6.8 times faster in case 8192 CPU cores are utilized. The current implementation results in strong speed-up because of two reasons: The imposition of parallel I/O and the change of communication protocol. The original ClustalW-MPI software is based of the serial POSIX-styled read and the information is passed to individual slave by the point-to-point operation. Since the master and slaves conduct completely isolated operations, the collective operation could not be imposed in the original version. On the other hand, the subroutine for data input should be accessed by all ranks for using parallel I/O, which also enables the use of collective communication calls. The replacement of point-to-point communication into collective one and fine tuning through the design of sub-groups provide the significant difference, especially when large amount of cores are used for the simulation. Since the current simulation time is the sum of all initial procedures, the net gain by current implementation should be much stronger than the ratio . We are convinced that the current implementation will contribute a lot on highly-parallelized sequence alignment implementations.

Figure 4 Wall-time Comparison between Sequential and Parallel I/O. Measured time is the total simulation time until all data inputs are broadcasted to all slaves.

4. Profiling ClustalW-MPI with Scalasca

In order to profile the parallel software ClustalW-MPI, the software tool Scalasca has been used [11], that supports performance optimization of parallel programs by measuring and analyzing their runtime behavior. The profile of the execution time of the original ClustalW-MPI software on JUQUEEN supercomputer for the case of 32768 cores is presented in Figure 5. The profile shows that the parallel system load is well balanced. The process rank 0 performs communication (Figure 6), synchronization (Figure 7) and data sending to all other processes. The proportion of execution time spent on each function is presented on the profiles in Figure 8. The performance estimation and profiling analyses have shown that the parallel system is well balanced both in respect to the workload and machine size except for the process rank 0 that is the most heavily utilized due to intensive communication and synchronization. Since this is the computation-intensive task, the overhead by the serial I/O is not considerably recognized by this profiling result.

Figure 5 Execution time profile of software ClustalW-MPI on JUQUEEN supercomputer, 32768 cores

Figure 6 Point-to-point communication profile for the ClustalW-MPI software run on JUQUEEN supercomputer, 32768 cores

Figure 7 Synchronization profile for the ClustalW-MPI software run on JUQUEEN supercomputer, 32768 cores

Figure 8 Proportion of time spent on each function

The molecular biology outcome of the experiments is that the consensus motifs and the variable domains in Influenza virus A have been determined and output by the Unipro UGENE editor [12] (Figure 9).

Figure 9 Finding out consensus and variable domains in the case of Human Influenza Virus A/H1N1; output by graphic editor Unipro UGENE

5. Conclusion and Future Works

The parallel software for multiple sequence alignment ClustalW-MPI has been optimized and ported on the supercomputer JUQUEEN through parallel reading data from files. Sequential reading from the master process and data distribution to slaves has been replaced by parallel reading utilizing MPI I/O functions. The slave processes are accessing the file for input operation.

Parallel performance evaluation and profiling of multiple sequence alignment software ClustalW-MPI and MPI I/O on the supercomputer JUQUEEN have been investigated experimentally. Parallel performance parameters such execution time, speedup and profiles have been estimated. The performance estimation and profiling analyses have shown that the parallel system is well balanced both in respect to the workload and machine size except for the process rank 0 that is the most heavily utilized due to intensive communication and synchronization.

Parallel reading via groups and effects of read buffer size have been investigated experimentally. Results indicate better performance compared with the composition of sequential read and broadcast operations. Comparison of the execution time in case of reading from the master process and data distribution to the slaves against execution time for parallel reading from file indicates the reduction of the time in case of parallel reading. The obtained performance utilizing the parallel read is stronger as the number of cores increases, so that it becomes 6.8 times faster than the original ClustalW-MPI implementation in case of using 8192 CPU cores. Our approach provides the stable and fast way of storing multiple sequence inputs, capacitating the alignment simulation of massive sequence datasets.

On the other hand, the part of the reading time from the overall time is not so significant, which is less than 2% in most cases. In this sense, increasing the performance of the software in terms of total execution time is not as significant and the benefit from advanced I/O operation is not much recognized from the overall performance since the code's master-slave parallelism prohibits large alignment simulation.

The problem size using ClustalW-MPI software is strictly limited by the number of sequences. Increasing input file size is limited due to allocated memory size (Juqueen's memory allocation per core is 1GB). Maximum number of input sequences is approximately 10000 (depending on the sequences size).

Overall conclusion from those experimental investigations is that in order to allow carrying out experiments using a large amount of data and to improve the performance it is necessary to change the type of parallelism. The change on parallelism from master-slave paradigm to SPMD paradigm (domain decomposition) looks essential for fully utilizing performance benefit from parallel read.

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Appendix A: Implementation of grouped I/O operation through the creation of sub-communicators

a) The way of creating the groups

```

// My rank and total number of processors
int rank, size;

// Leader processors
int leader;

// MPI basics
MPI_Init(&argc, &argv);
MPI_Comm_rank(MPI_COMM_WORLD, &rank);
MPI_Comm_size(MPI_COMM_WORLD, &size);

// Set up leader: probably the master rank in each node
leader = 0;
if(rank % CORE_PER_NODE == 0) leader = 1;

// Create new groups!!!!
MPI_Group all_procs, leaders, slaves, subgroup; // All cores in MPI_COMM_WORLD
MPI_Comm leader_comm, loc_comm;

MPI_Comm_group(MPI_COMM_WORLD, &all_procs);

int leader_id=size;
int loc_id=CORE_PER_NODE;

{
    int *lead_list;
    int locsiz = (size-1)/CORE_PER_NODE + 1;
    lead_list = (int *) malloc (locsiz * sizeof(int));
    for(i=0; i<locsiz; i++) lead_list[i]=i*CORE_PER_NODE;
    MPI_Group_incl(all_procs, locsiz, lead_list, &leaders);
    MPI_Comm_create(MPI_COMM_WORLD, leaders, &leader_comm);
    MPI_Group_rank(leaders, &leader_id);
    free(lead_list);
}

{
    int *lead_list;
    int locsca = (size-1)/CORE_PER_NODE + 1;
    int locloc = rank/CORE_PER_NODE + 1;
    int locsiz = CORE_PER_NODE;
    if(locsca == locloc) locsiz = (size-1)%CORE_PER_NODE + 1;
    lead_list = (int *) malloc (locsiz * sizeof(int));
    for(i=0; i<locsiz; i++) lead_list[i]=(locloc-1)*CORE_PER_NODE+i;
    MPI_Group_incl(all_procs, locsiz, lead_list, &subgroup);
    MPI_Comm_create(MPI_COMM_WORLD, subgroup, &loc_comm);
    MPI_Group_rank(subgroup, &loc_id);
    free(lead_list);
}

// MPI-IO Operations are done over 'leader_comm' communicator, and stored information at local masters are distributed over 'loc_comm'

```

b) Read Operation by the Groups

```

// Variables
MPI_File in;
MPI_Offset filesize, offset;
MPI_Status status;
int read_buffer = 16777216; // Read buffer size
int ierr;

// Get file size
// File open by all
ierr = MPI_File_open(MPI_COMM_WORLD, Filename,
                    MPI_MODE_RDONLY, MPI_INFO_NULL, &in);

MPI_File_get_size(in, &filesize);

```

```

    int length = (int) filesize;

    MPI_File_close(&in);
// End of get file size

// Parallel read
// Memory allocation
    char *chunk;
    chunk = (char*) malloc ((length+2)*sizeof(char));

// Size of file read
    int LocRead = MIN (length,read_buffer);

// Leader reads
if(leader)
{
    ierr = MPI_File_open(leader_comm, Filename,
        MPI_MODE_RDONLY, MPI_INFO_NULL, &in);

// Number of loops
    loop = filesize/LocRead + 1;

// Looped read
    for(j = 0; j < loop; j++) {

// For reading with MPI_read
        offset = (MPI_Offset) j * LocRead;
        readsize = (int) ( MIN ( (j+1)*LocRead, length ) - offset);
        MPI_File_set_view(in, offset, MPI_BYTE, MPI_BYTE,
            "native", MPI_INFO_NULL);

// Line reading for MPI_read
        readlines (&in, rank, offset, readsize, &chunk);

    } // End of looped read

// Close the file
    MPI_File_close(&in);

} // End of leader read

// Broadcasting to all ranks in the same group
    MPI_Bcast(&chunk[0],length,MPI_BYTE,0,loc_comm);
// End of parallel read

// Subroutine to be called
void readlines (MPI_File *in, const int rank, MPI_Offset offset,
    int readsize, char **lines)
{
    MPI_Status status;
    MPI_File_read_all(*in, &(*lines)[offset], readsize,
        MPI_BYTE, &status);
    return;
}
// End of read subroutine

```